

STUDY OF DISCOURSE AND SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF ALLEGORY

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Abstract: Allegorical means are found not only in fiction, but also in speech, painting, art and many other fields. The main purpose of this article is to show that allegory is not only a means of artistic representation, but also has functions such as simile and irony.

Key words: allegory, symbol, simile, artistic image, style, methodology

An exact repetition of any event in existence has not been created. There are even about 1,000,000 snowflakes per square meter with a thickness of 50 cm. However, even though the entire surface of the earth is covered with snow, no snowflake is identical in shape. This fact was revealed in 1985 in the conclusion of 50 years of observations and experiments of the American researcher Wilson Bentley. Today, it is clear to many that there are no similar voices, faces, and finger tips.

Based on this unique law of life, it is impossible for two writers (poets) to be the same or people who think exactly the same. Because the internal and external structure of every created person is a unique universe, its uniqueness is embodied in itself. Based on this, the world of every person - life experience, level of knowledge, taste, ability to see beauty, imagination, world of fantasy, eye of the soul belongs to him and this identity is reflected in his every speech or work. Therefore, the concept of "Style is a person" (Getyo) is valid and vital. Based on this, V.G. Belinsky believes that style is the ability of the writer to give form and content a concrete state and, at the same time, to leave his personality, his soul, and his unrepeatable stamp on everything.

Style is content, form, idea, and motive at the same time. When all this is combined, the style ensures the integrity of the work. Accordingly, it is inappropriate to connect the writer's style to words, language - to the originality of their use. It is true that literature is the art of words, and language is the first element of literature, but it is considered one of the tools that create style - a necessary element. One of the most necessary factors that create style is related to the speaker's ability to research and analyze life, its essence and the truth behind it. The art of discovering the rich and hidden secrets of the human psyche, their fundamental aesthetic value, is directly related to the knowledge of the psyche.

Therefore, the style is the writer's perception of reality and man, the discovery of the truth in their hearts and the ability to express it figuratively through words - it is the art of individual creation of these tasks. The style always originates from the speaker's whole existence - his nature, and in each of his creations, he revives the life-giving light of this unique world - humanized feelings, shares it with others, acts as an educator of noble feelings. That is why the style cannot show itself openly in the works of a "weak writer". The styles of weak writers resemble each other" (Fitrat, p. 26). "Style changes with time as it changes with personality.

Allegory, metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, simile, paraphrase, irony and onomatopoeia are not only artistic image tools, but also stylistic tropes. Because the tools make the text more attractive and colorful, the reader can understand the information quickly and easily. Also, the mentioned stylistic tools are not only a part of linguistics but also used in the special literature of literary studies as symbols in different meanings. We can find these means of expression

not only in linguistics or fiction, but also in art, historical or religious sources, and in our daily speech. Artistic pictorial means ensure that the addressee understands the information quickly and easily and enriches our language. One such figurative tool is allegory.

If we define this concept, then the allegory will be: an artistic device, that is, its essence is to express an abstract concept through a clear, vivid image. Perhaps the most common example of allegory is an image of death in the form of a skull and bones or a figure in black with a scythe... Allegorical images were used by artists from the Middle Ages and the Renaissance to the nineteenth century. widely used in their works. In modern art, interesting allusions are very skillfully used to express the meaning of the work in a more subtle, invisible way, allowing the viewer to understand the hidden hint of the author himself. This is the role of the cinema. Allegory is not only found in literary speech. Perhaps, we ourselves, often without realizing it, use figurative expressions in our daily life.

. For example, "The first swallow" is a sign of approaching good changes, a new and long-awaited event. Or "indebtedly" - a person who tries to pretend that he is important, irreplaceable, important, even though he is not. Allegory has been found in literature since ancient times. Homer's poems "Odyssey" and "Iliad", where the allegorical image of Odysseus is identified with the curious, inexhaustible mind of man, and his wife Penelope as the impressive and undeniable image of love, loyalty and womanhood. loyalty In the works of the ancient Greek fabulist Aesop, irony was used: animals were described, the author mocked, paraded the greed, deception and stupidity of people. Later, his figurative speech style was called Aesopian.

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